

Faceted Curve Cross-Laminated Timber Interlocking Angle-Planed and Kerf Curved Lamellas: Construction Principles, Prototype, Variants, Uses and Fabrications.

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Abstract:

This document presents a novel methodology for producing non-flat, faceted, three-dimensionally profiled and curved cross-laminated timber elements. The structural elements relies on layered timber lamellas arranged in cross-directional geometry, where in one direction standard flat lamellas —or finger-jointed lumber— are planed with an angle on their lateral faces. In the other direction, kerf-curved dimensional lumber —or finger-jointed lumber— pieces are set, glued, nailed, doweled and/or screwed, interlocking thus the faceted geometry of the entire element in the correspondent plane. By kerf-curving lamellas with a desired angle, and a desired faceting distance that match with the width of the flat lamellas in the other direction, each panel-element can achieve any radius starting from around 50 cm.

The disclosed methodology introduces both affordable equivalent variations —where nails or dowels provide linkage and pressure to bond lamellas, with or without adhesive, without the use of heavy-duty pressing machines— and non-budget-limited variations where heavy-duty machines can be used as per traditional CLT, on special faceted-curved molds, glued only, allowing to obtain panels that reach the full structural potential.

Despite the affordable variations are pre-deemed as non-reaching-full-structural-potential, this document argues that the methodology for these variations are relevant since structural capacity handicap is compensated by the inherent advantages of curved elements for some load scenarios, the affordability issues, and biophilic neuro-architecture advantages that curved with small faceting can offer to society in general and certain users in particular.

Applying geometric and material tests, the methodology provides a faceted curve, non-flat mass timber CLT alternative for load-bearing walls, partitions, vaulted roofs, slabs and self-supporting envelopes.

Keywords: Faceted curved cross-laminated timber, FCCLT, Faceted Curved CLT, Non-Flat CLT, Screwed CLT, Faceted curved DLT, Faceted curved nailed cross-laminated timber, FCNCLT, Faceted CLT, Kerf-curved CLT, FCDLT, Kerf-Curved Cross-Laminated Timber, FKCCLT, KCCLT, Construction, Mass timber, A Campo Traviesa, AEC industry.

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Construction Principles

Kerf-curving a finger jointed or dimensional lumber is a well-known carpentry process. Grooves performed by a saw, or two different thicknesses saws, or a router with a conical bit, carves timber's faces. Helped or not with steam or hot water, the originally flat piece of timber 'can then easily make a curve'. In fact, it performs both an almost imperceptible perfect curve behind the grooves (Figure 3), while primary, the resulting geometry is a faceted curve.

Grooves are filled with glue (orange hatch, Figure 5) and kept press-curved at desired bending position to recover certain strength properties of the timber that were diminished due to the fact grooves cut longitudinal fibers. That reduction depends on factors such as the depth of the grooves, the specie and specific timber element nature and the structural properties of the used glue, among others.

Kerf curved dimensional lumber are often used for concrete formwork for faceted 'curved' beams, are affordable and require time-consuming carpentry process. For a reasonable industrial point of view, however, grooves can be performed very rapidly if aligning lamellas on a table, where saws or routers can groove several boards at once in a semi-automated process, or by aligning and CNC grooving for an automated, more expensive, process.

Groove's depth, or better said, the thickness remaining without groove, must be chosen considering the desired ratio of the faceting curve needed, the timber grade and specie, and

the bending system chosen. Groove's width too. Softwoods such as pine, spruce among others are commonly suitable. The prototype was made with 30.0x5.5mm clear *Paraná's* pine sourced from young-aged plantations The groove depth was 3.5mm, thus 2mm was the remaining depth where lamella finds continuity.

In order to illustrate the simpler possible shape to substantiate this methodology, it is possible and affordable to set equal spacing and equal lamellas widths, and a constant ratio curvature. The prototype opted for this configuration. Thus, equal groove depths at fixed distances were set. This is the case also for the isometric views (Figure 1 and 2), where drawings represent a panel of 8 'vertical' Layer 1 plus 8 'vertical' Layer 3 slight smaller lamellas, 9 kerf-curved Layer 2 lamellas, angle $\vartheta=2^\circ$ (Figure 3), for a total example panel of $t=63\text{mm}$, height= 1089mm , ratio of 1763mm and outer chord of 980.3mm (width). Dimensions are relevant for proportions of this example. Kerf-curved lamellas have 121mm (height), setting grooves each 120mm . Inner layer 3 faces have 118.56mm and outer Layer 1 faces (b in Figure 5) have 122.9mm . Panel-elements can be made in varied dimensions. E.g.: $3000 \times 12000\text{ mm}$ and t around 20, 45, 60, 80, 100, 140, 200 mm etc.

Figure 1. One panel isometric view.

Figure 2. Exploded Isometric view.

The Figure 2 highlights ‘vertical’ Layers 1 and 3. Layer 2 in this case, kerf-curved, has ‘vertical’ lines that represent the grooves. See prototype process to see how lines are in fact visible.

The kerf-curved lamellas defines an inner and outer profile. As explained before, the outer profile may likely depict a very subtle curve behind the remaining timber depth, being it less than 2mm, not offering geometry problems for most of the cases. The outer faceted faces are wider than the inner ones. It means that, i.e., on a 3-layer system, the layer 1 should arrive to the manufacture process with some mm more in width than the layer 3, being the layer 2, the kerf-curved lamellas.

Lamellas of layer 1 and 3—or better said, flat lamellas not kerf curved, generally layers 1, 3, 5 and so on— receive an angled finish on long sides, by cutting it or as per the prototype, planing them with a sand. These parallel long sides (Figures 3 and 4) must be defined as per the desired ratio of the panel needed. All dimensions mentioned here are reference only: angles, t, ratio, etc., are up to each project need. Figure 3 angle ϑ equals 2° .

Gluing grooves of dimensional lumber to desired faceted curves, provide faceted lamellas that can withstand cross sectional demands—shear and internal forces of the panel itself—since fibers run perpendicular to layer 1 and 3 with excellent strength for most of the loading scenarios where CLT are used, thanks to the help of an adequate adhesive-glue at grooves.

For most of the cases, tests are recommended to be performed for the entire panel, with its specific chosen thickness. The prototype was tested. More tests should occur within next months and years to comprehensively record characteristics values of variants. The test was

performed under simple conditions. However, the results are coherent with what can be expected, showing that the solutions is stable, structural and preserves panel's integrity.

Figure 3. Plan view of example 1.

The Figure 3 highlights lateral faces to be planed, for all Layer 1 and 3 lamellas. This variant requires cutting or sanding both long lateral faces of each, at θ angle. Kerf-curved requires thus 2θ angle bent. The figure highlight also the mentioned curve, approx.. 2 mm, behind the groove made to kerf-curve the lamella. After that curve, which is absorbed by tolerances, the faces are straight, faceted.

Figure 4. Plan view of example 2.

The Figure 4 highlight lateral faces to be planed, for all Layer 1 and 3 lamellas. This variant requires cutting or sanding one long lateral face of each, at ψ angle. Kerf-curved requires thus ψ angle bent. The figure also highlights small steps located at Layer 1, as a result of this simplified one face sand/cut. Tolerances might absorb this difference: in the scaled prototype, steps are absorbed within general tolerances. L1 (Layer 1), L2 and L3 highlighted.

Geometry here reflects deviations and tolerances as per the scale prototype made. Drawing scale thus is larger than previous figure.

Figure 5. Detailed plan view of example 1.

Above Figure cuts a panel at nails level. Nails can be replaced by another variant mentioned (p. 15). Figure highlights an optional 2-nail on a faceted face rectangle. In this case, dimension 'b' = 122.99 mm (as reference) as mentioned. Thickness $t = 63\text{mm}$. Figure also highlight alternated wood grain, fiber orientation.

The key assumption is that curved or faceted-curve CLT (FCCLT) using adhesive only, would require molds matching with pressing technology for each ratio, and projects' needs are different, making it non-standardized, thus expensive. That limits and prevent using faceted and curved CLT. Thus, with a less monolithic variant, which by its interlocking layering still offers integrity, affordable FCCLT can be relevant, even at in-situ assembled approaches, allowing offering to society curved elements, curved spaces. It is assumed that curved walls, roofs, etc., are always needed in construction, and that demand is increasing due to the benefit of curved timber elements for biophilic and neuro-architectural reasons. The fact that affordable 'low-tech' variants do not reach the full structural potential of a traditional CLT do not mean they can be useful to the market and can indeed satisfy society needs. Also, under most load scenarios, panel's curved form adds structural performance because of its shape, an advantage not frequent —lost— in flat CLT panels.

Scaled Prototype

Materials:

- . Clear pinewood from Paraná-BR, sourced from young-aged plantations, planed lumber
- . Contact glue with organic solvents
- . Carbon-steel nails of 13x1mm, 2mm head diameter

Geometry:

Layer 1 and 3: 30x5.5x150mm lamellas, total 8 pieces

Layer 2: 30x5.5x118mm lamellas, kerf-curved, total 5 pieces

Grooves: each 29mm

Groove's depth: 2 saw system, 3.5x1 and 1.5x2mm

Ratio: 340 mm from center to inner edge

Nails spacing: 30 x 29 mm

Total own weight: 145 grams

Tolerances: +/- 0.5mm.

Figure 6. Prototype's inner side.

Figure 7. Prototype's outer side and nail.

Grooves were done with 1 mm saw, till the 3.5mm desired depth, plus a 2mm width saw, till 1.5mm depth,

This dual saw selection was in order to break longitudinal grain fibers to the smaller extent. Ideally, a triangular groove by a conical router can be preferred.

For layer 1 lamellas, the angle-planed faces were performed without diminishing the outer width. The inner width defined the fixed distance for the grooves.

For layer 4 lamellas, the angle-planed faces were performed diminishing the outer width in order to match the inner profile of the layer 2 faceted lamellas. It means, layer 3 lamellas required higher amount of waste to reduce their width. It can be avoided by selecting a certain width for Layer 1 and a slightly narrower width for Layer 3 lamellas, depending of course on the ratio of the element.

The resulting thickness behind the grooves of Layer 2 lamellas was about 1.8 mm. Lamellas were submerged for 5 minutes in 65°C water. It allowed to easy bending them. Artisan pressing molds were used due to the small size. Glue was introduce in the grooves and the curve was kept for 24 hours. Pressure applied was very small compared to industrial heavy-duty pressing machines. The result and micron-deviation was acceptable. Micron-deviations, tolerances, ended up by being coherent in general as per the results obtained (see tests). For other panel dimensions, absolute tolerances might remain unchanged, meaning bigger lamellas and panels should present superior performances.

Figure 8. Scaled prototype sequence.

The Figure 8 above highlights layering: upper left, 5 layer 3 lamellas present aligned grooves before bending. Upper right, 4 layer 1 lamellas are glued through their planed long lateral faces, helped by red-lines-marked auxiliary supports to land in its curved shape. Bottom-left image shows kerf-curved lamellas being glued with layer 1. Bottom-right, shows layer 3 lamellas joining this 3-layer example.

Laminating sequence: it consisted of using glue between all faces, in order to gain some adherence before nailing. The amount of glues was the minimum to maintain the shape. To do so, supports were set beneath the Layer 1. In most cases, a faceted table of the desired geometry (mold) might be preferred. Positioning layer 1 and 2 was straightforward and simple even with imprecise mold (support) since the angled-planed and kerf-curved profile matched, thus both layer geometries 'embraced' each other. After 2 hours, when glue was still drying, the 3rd layer was glued with minimum glue, and then nailed. Nailing was performed with one nail at the center of each 30 x 29 mm flat face (considering the kerf-curved lamellas 30mm width). It encompassed all 3 layers, from the layer 3. Nails worked, however, spectrum of tiny nails' lengths are limited. A longer nail would be preferred. The precision in all dimensions, angles, etc., are key for the 3 layers and each of its pieces: to fit the three dimensional 'puzzle'. Nails (and/or screws if needed and extra clamping) or dowels come to confirm that match and to guarantee that glue count with a certain amount of pressure to dry for the next 24 or more hours.

One option is to set 2 nails per faceted face, one from each side, or dowels. Anyways, as per the prototype, a monolithic panel is achieved.

Loads were added to the panel in a vaulted position in order to test it. High performance was observed considering its thickness (16.5mm).

The bending strength test (Figure 9, 10, 11, 12) was performed fixing one side (x, z) and letting the other one freely in the x direction. The z direction was pinned at the right end since a table was set beneath. In the middle of the vault a mass of 10 Kg was added. With it, deflection was observed and measured. This test was performed 3 times: deflection observed was approximately the same for all three. Z lowered by 2.5mm. Square marks of a paper behind are each 5mm. The deflections were compared to an original default position where the panel withstand only its own weight (Figure 9).

Another test performed was as shown in Figure (13). The panel did not show any deflection, keeping its integrity, under 10kg axial, eccentric load.

These tests were carried out without strict mechanisms, thus, it was not necessary nor reasonable to extend it. Rather, they were useful for its limited goals, validates the panel obtained and encourages further tests in next months and years. Observations are useful to depict how promising this new methodology can be for slabs, vaults, etc. For vertical walls under gravitational loads, a load test can be performed, preferably linking it to slabs or beams, in order to assess typical whole system behavior. In advance, the prototype panel is useful to handle perfectly axial loads. Values should be coherent regarding timber specie used. That is why bending test is highlighted, since deformation and internal stress of angled geometry between pieces are more clearly visible for this documental stage.

The 'scaled prototype' is in fact a real scale Faceted Curve CLT panel. It is called 'scaled' because despite being composed by dimensional lumber, in general, common dimension will be 2 times bigger or more. That is why the prototype with 5.5mm thickness lamellas is

optionally called 'scaled'. Since principles are the same for mentioned thicknesses, for 3, 5 or more layers, and any typical dimensions similar to CLT flat panels dimensions, this prototype embodies the solution.

For those other dimensions the methodology is the same. The prototype allowed to obtain a 150 x 118 x 16.5 mm mass timber affordable faceted-curve panel.

Bearing capacities will vary from panel to panel, its thickness, specie, adhesive, correct screwing/nailing and spacing, etc. The test served as an example, confirming that in common dimensions, panels will be stable, strong and relevant as structural members: walls, slabs, etc.

Figure 9. Prototype bending test, original position.

Figure 10. Prototype bending test, 10kg loaded.

Figure 11. Prototype bending test with arrows

Figure 12. Flexion bending test diagram with deformations.

Figure 13. Eccentric load test diagram.

Figure 14. Prototype's curvature shown.

Figure 15. Plan view.

To better illustrate the faceted curve obtained, the two above Figures 14 and 15 are offered. The h dimension of figure 14 highlights the z obtained through this example of faceted curved CLT. Figure 15 is a plan view where the panel was kept in Figure 14 position, to

reference the nail exact position no measure h. 2kg load was set at one corner to secure the position.

Fabrication: Variants, Geometries

All variants here are presented with uneven layer as flat dimensional lumber and even layers as kerf-curved lumber. It can be set the opposite way, however, the panel will be less affordable.

The main variants are those already mentioned: screwed plus nails, nailed or doweled only, with or without adhesive, or adhesive-only panels. All faceted kerf-curved cross directional lamellas and planed long faces of lamellas in the other direction.

Varied manufacturing process differ in some of the steps as already mentioned (heavy-duty CNC machines are optional, as well as pressing machines). Principles of interlocking geometries remain the same for all.

Another kind of variants are related to the selection of softwoods or hardwoods, despite fir, spruce and pine are recommended. Also, obviously, panel's dimensions and curvature ratio, will output variants, or better said, panel's dimensions.

In order to offer a refined solution regarding fire-protection at detail, nailing/screwing letting space for wood plugs can be adopted, to avoid surface carbonizing around the nail head. Fire-protection timing and strategies as a whole may vary for projects strategies, local norms and the inclusions of another finishing layer / letting the panel visible.

Is interesting to notice that even considering the fact that this new methodology is not curve *stricto sensu*, but a faceted profile that resembles a curve, from a certain distance and ratios over 150 cm, it can be perceived as curved elements. Even when outer and inner lamellas (not kerf-curved ones) are relatively wide and with ratios of about 100 cm or more, the faceted wall, slab, or vault, will probably be helpful as a neuro-sensible element with almost the same effects than perfectly curved walls, slabs or vaults.

For a given ratio, the narrower the selection of the angle-planed flat lamellas width, the more kerf-curve grooves will be needed, resulting in both a more time consuming and more expensive panel, but a softer faceted curve achieved.

As done with the prototype, both glue and nails can be used. Minimum glue, e.g. used for the prototype, means a very thin layer of glue that barely touches all faces of interlocking pieces. Its goal is to help in manufacturing nailing process by keeping the pieces together at the correct position. It also, of course, will act together with nails/screws/dowels when facing any type of load. Adhesive can be used generously, not-minimum, if desired. Nails (plus some screws help or not) will help to let it dry being pressed, for 24 days or weeks. Fasteners are recommended to be set perpendicular to each face, as per the scaled prototype. Angled

insertions are possible. In all cases, the principle is to coherent respect the three dimensional configuration so all fasteners are at the same position related the face that host them, resulting in a fastened 3D matrix.

Recommended nails are those high-bonding with annular ring or helical threads.

Terminology can adopt the already mentioned FCCLT or FCDLT (faceted curve dowel laminated timber) or FCNCLT (faceted curve nail cross-laminated timber) or FKCCLT (faceted kerf-curved cross-laminated timber), etc., up to the manufacturer.

Lastly, it is foreseeable that affordable versions can use treated-for-outdoor lumber. Treatment can occur right before laminating all lamellas.

Field of Use

It can be helpful as load bearing walls, partitions, building envelopes, slabs, cantilevered terraces, roof vaults, Catalan-vault slabs and floors, thin-tile vault slabs, partitions and modular low-cost components assembled on-site.

Open-Source Innovation and Good-Faith Announcements

This document is published as an open-source architectural, engineering and material innovation. The author hereby dedicates this methodology and technical data to the public domain. The aim behind this perfectible document is to communicate a solution that was worked up weeks ago. Communicating this new methodology for faceted curve mass timber elements can allow any manufacturer to obtain a reliable building material solution, without royalties or licensing fees, etc.

Prior Art Notice: To the best of author's knowledge after searches performed, no identical or equivalent interlocking non-flat CLT systems or panels currently exist in registers, market or academic literature. This document establishes an official timestamped record of prior art for its novel. Since CLT is in public domain after 1920s original inventions —US patent 1465245, Watts, R. L. and Wars, F. J.— plus modern 1990s academic researchers —Schickhofer, G. (1994) TU Graz and Kreuzinger, H. TUM— and perfectly curve CLT exists, no faceted-curve cross-laminated panels were found in searches. While making them may probably been already executed without patents, considering CLT has no patents valid today, this novel methodology may has never been used nor published or patented as per its interlocking system with kerf-curved lamellas and planed-angle faces. This is why 'kerf-curved' word appears in abstract, title and keywords and is the key for the methodology affordability, acting together with planed faces.

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It is expected that the disclosed methodology, with its principles, variants and resulting panels, are worth in the sense of introducing affordable faceted curve mass timber elements with structural, biophilic and neuro-sensible architecture capabilities.